

A Traumatic Testimony: Saadat Hasan Manto's "Toba Tek Singh"

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Abstract

The desire of expressing one's trauma and the compulsion to resist revelation is an ongoing conflict within an individual. Saadat Hasan Manto's narrative in "Toba Tek Singh" is a negotiation between the two, not just for himself but for an entire people as he manages to evoke a discussion between silence (loss of language) and testimony. His text reiterates that it is difficult to separate personal and collective trauma. Originally written in Urdu, this short story is a narrative of the dilemma of Bishan Singh, who in post partition of India and Pakistan in 1947, wants to know on which side of the borderline his village Toba Tek Singh is?

Keywords: *trauma studies, testimony, partition literature, religion, Saadat Hasan Manto, Sigmund Freud, seduction theory.*

The 1990s stirred the development of trauma studies into motion. This first wave relied heavily on Sigmund Freud's psychoanalytic theory of trauma. Also referred to as the traditional trauma model, it was pioneered by Cathy Caruth, Shoshana Felman, and Geoffrey Hartman. They put forth the idea that trauma is essentially a suffering that is beyond representation. The traditional model of trauma had a profound impact on the concept of trauma in literary criticism especially with the publication of Cathy Caruth's *Unclaimed Experience: Trauma, Narrative, and History* and Kali Tal's *World of Hurt: Reading the Literatures of Trauma* which pioneered the psychoanalytic post structural approach. But trauma studies were eventually enriched by alternate models and methodologies that offered revised claims. There was a major shift as these new models made the suggestion of determinate value existing within traumatic experience. A key development in this context was the emergence of the pluralistic model of trauma, that it is by dint of a variety of representational modes that knowledge and value are located in traumatic experience.

One of the most poignant and candid voices in the Partition discourse is that of Saadat Hasan Manto, who believes in telling it as it is. He lives up to the task that Felman assigns to a historian when she writes in her essay "Benjamin's Silence,"

. . . the task of the historian is to reconstruct what history has silenced, to give voice to the dead and to the vanquished and to resuscitate the unrecorded, silenced, hidden story of the oppressed. (213-14)

Manto's stories in *Kingdom's End and Other Stories* incorporate within a telling tale of the partition trauma. His "Toba Tek Singh" too is an embodiment of this trauma. Originally written in Urdu, this short story is a narrative of the dilemma of Bishan Singh, who wants to know where his village Toba Tek Singh is, and the setting of the story is a lunatic asylum in Lahore.

A dark comedy set in post partition, "Toba Tek Singh" touches upon the ridiculousness of the aspect of colonial India having been divided upon religious lines, as

the exchange of the inmates of lunatic asylums, much like the prisoners, is also being discussed by the governments of India and Pakistan.

Manto's reputation as a radical who edged towards the leftist-socialist beliefs, is far from being shed through this stingingly satirical short story either. He looks at lunacy in a new light, turning it into an extended metaphor of institutional insanity. Partition was a horrific event that scared generations with the unprecedented violence. There were riots, massacres, rapes, abductions, forced migrations, displacement, exile, refugee crisis, forced suicides, and extreme helplessness in the face of it all. This left behind victims, eyewitnesses, and memory. In this story, Manto depicts the aftermath to these events and he does not shy away from portraying those who had engineered the violence. He creates a discourse against the criminal impostors who had taken refuge in the asylum in order to evade conviction.

It is not the experience itself that produces traumatic effect but rather the remembrance of it. The Lahore lunatic asylum inhabits a number of patients who seem to be dealing with a traumatic past. And to put it in Jean-Max Gaudilliere's words "They are the event" (*Listening to Trauma* 83). Or just as Francoise Davoine states, "These people are the memory" (*Listening to Trauma* 83). And it is noteworthy how Manto creates the identity of these persons based on religion. In a rather tongue in cheek way Manto recounts one Muslim lunatic, "a regular leader of the fire-eating daily newspaper *Zamindar*," who when asked about what according to him Pakistan was, with profound reflection replies that it is a place where cut throat razors were manufactured (Manto 11).

Yet another notable fabrication of his pen is a conversation between two Sikh lunatics. When one asks the other as to, Why they were being sent to India when they did not know the language that was spoken there? the person questioned replies with a smile that he knew the language of the "Hindostoras." "These devils" he declares, "always strut about as if they were the lords of the earth" (Manto 12).

A Muslim lunatic, while bathing, raises the slogan of "*Pakistan Zindabad*" in such an enthusiastic manner that he loses his footing, and is later found lying unconscious on the floor. Manto creates an intriguingly profound and satirically charged atmosphere as he declares that even the inmates who were feigning madness were clueless about the situation.

... They probably had a vague idea why India was being divided and what Pakistan was, but, as for the present situation, they were clueless. [...]

As to where Pakistan was located, the inmates knew nothing. That was why both the mad and the partially mad were unable to decide whether they were now in India or in Pakistan. If they were in India, where on earth was Pakistan? And if they were in Pakistan, then how come that until only the other day it was India? (Manto 12)

Manto heightens the sense of the loss of identity and the forgetfulness of traumatic partition, as he creates a character of a specific inmate, who "caught up in this India-Pakistan-Pakistan-India rigmarole," one of those days, installed himself on a branch of a tree and kept speaking on the "delicate" India- Pakistan issue for two hours straight, and when the guards attempted to persuade him, to get to the ground, he instead went on to mount a higher branch (Manto 12). Furthermore, when the guards resorted to threatening him with punishment he declared: "I wish to live neither in India nor in Pakistan. I wish to live in this tree" (Manto 13). A rather profound ecofeminist statement indeed, but through this very statement, Manto also manages to let this lunatic come out of his silence, just as the story itself becomes Manto's testimony and an act of recording his own history.

It is a rather cathartic culmination of this event, in which one is moved to deep emotion, as the lunatic is finally persuaded to come down and upon doing so he immediately begins to embrace his Sikh and Hindu friends, religious identities that Manto

does not allow the readers to forget at any moment. Tears start running down his cheeks as he is overcome by sadness that his friends were about to leave him and go to India.

As an aftermath to the government decision and debate, in another incident, Manto depicts a Muslim radio engineer, who holds an M.Sc. degree, loves to take long walks, and never socialises with anyone, one day take off his clothes and upon handing the bundle to one of the attendants in the asylum, runs around naked in the garden.

Manto's creative satirical jibes do not stop just here. He goes on to create yet another memorable inmate in the form of a Muslim lunatic from Chaniot, who is described as one of the most devoted workers of the All India Muslim League, and is given to obsessive bathing, ranging up to fifteen or sixteen times a day. But post this decision, and as a reaction to the debate, had responded in his own way by completely ditching his set ways. He had suddenly stopped bathing and announced himself to be—*Quaid-e-Azam* Mohamed Ali Jinnah. As a consequence to his declaration, a Sikh inmate declared himself to be Master Tara Singh, the leader of the Sikhs. All this led the authorities to apprehend serious communal trouble and prompted them to curb the dangerous behaviour of the inmates by locking them up in separate cells.

Among those stirring the communal trouble was also a young Hindu lawyer from Lahore who had “gone off his head after an unhappy love affair” (Manto 13). But upon being exposed to the news of the latest developments, and how Amritsar was to be a part of India, he was pushed further into depression. This was mainly because his beloved lived in Amritsar and associated memories had never escaped him even in his madness. The day he had learnt of the partition, he had mouthed obscenities against every Hindu and Muslim leader who was responsible for it because this had affected his relationship with his beloved who as a consequence now was an Indian and he a Pakistani. But the recent news of the exchange of inmates amongst the two countries brought a happy twist for him according to his inmate friends who began congratulating him as he would now be sent to India, the land of his beloved. However, as a further twist to his plight, Manto has this character declare that he had no intentions of leaving Lahore now as his practice, as a lawyer, would not flourish in Amritsar.

After equipping the reader with this rich imaginary scene of the Lahore asylum Manto leads us to the key figure of this story, Bishan Singh. Yet another inmate in the asylum, his identity has been established as a Sikh who had been confined there for the past fifteen years. And very peculiarly, according to the guards, the man had not slept or even winked in these past years of his stay. However occasionally he was spotted leaning against a wall. Due to his constant standing his legs had swollen but the man remained unfazed. Manto informs his audience that Bishan Singh had lately taken to listening to discussions pertaining to the “forthcoming exchange of Indian and Pakistani lunatics” but had still not emerged out of his verbal repetition of almost nonsensical language.

Making a little variation from his repetitive but occasional mysterious gibberish of saying: “Uper the gur gur the annex the bay dhayana the mung the dal of the laltain,” after listening about the upcoming exchange of the inmates, he solemnly states his opinion in his signature gibberish: “Uper the gur gur the annex the bay dhayana the mung the dal of the Government of Pakistan” (Manto 14). This senseless verbal banter is equivalent to silence. He emerges as the marginal voice, choked in the face of its traumatic experience.

Manto reveals Bishan Singh's concern about finding out if his village Toba Tek Singh, fell in India or Pakistan. Manto beautifully portrays his dilemma recounting the scenario through a wider picture that he creates:

Of late, however, the Government of Pakistan had been replaced by the Government of Toba Tek Singh, a small town in the Punjab which was his home. He had also begun enquiring where Toba Tek Singh was to go. However, nobody was quite sure

whether it was in India or Pakistan. Those who had tried to solve this mystery had utterly confused when told that Sialkot, which used to be in India, was now in Pakistan. It was anybody's guess what was going to happen to Lahore, which was currently in Pakistan, but could slide into India any moment. It was also possible that the entire subcontinent of India might become Pakistan. And who could say if both India and Pakistan might not entirely vanish from the map of the world one day?" (Manto 14)

Manto's description of Bishan Singh's countenance is symbolic of the state of affairs in the divided parts of his native land: "The old man's hair was almost gone and what little was left had become a part of the beard, ... a strange, ... frightening, appearance" (Manto 14-15). This exterior is carefully contrasted with his "harmless" interior for the man had never gotten into a fight with anyone during his stay. A fairly prosperous landlord, he had suddenly gone mad, and had to be brought in fetters to the asylum by his family.

During the initial period of his stay he used to receive visitors but they had waned post the stirring of communal unrest in Punjab. And almost reciprocal to this is his gradual loss of identity within his immediate surroundings. He had acquired the name, Toba Tek Singh. The idea is further intensified by Manto when he introduces his name almost midway through the narrative or when he is constantly referred to as the "Sikh lunatic" before that. He may have been in a state of limbo for years being oblivious to time but he had developed a sixth sense which would help him sense the day he would be visited by his family and friends (Manto 15). But even during those anticipated and much awaited meetings he would express only in his usual gibberish. His confinement had meant leaving a fifteen year old daughter behind and slowly in the strange world he had come to inhabit, "hers was just another face" (Manto 15). He was distressed and desperately wanted to know about his village's whereabouts on the map but he was becoming used to not receiving any satisfactory responses. Nobody in the vicinity knew of its true status. The "...visits had...stopped. He was increasingly restless, but, more than that, curious. The sixth sense, which used to alert him to the day of the visit, had also atrophied" (Manto 15).

In an interesting conversation between Bishan Singh and an inmate, who had declared himself God, about the whereabouts of Toba Tek Singh, the megalomaniacal lunatic chuckled saying: "Neither in India nor in Pakistan, because, so far, we have issued no orders in this respect" (Manto 16). Bishan Singh could not help himself but beg this lunatic whom he seemed to believe to be 'God' to issue the necessary orders so as to be relieved of his problem but is only netted out with more disappointment as this 'God' in front of him appeared to be preoccupied with some more pressing matters. So angrily Bishan Singh tells this imposter: "Uper the gur gur the annexe the mung the dal of Guruji da Khalsa and Guruji ki fateh...jo boley so nihal sat sri akal" (Manto 16). In this moment Manto clarified that: "What he wanted to say was: 'You don't answer my prayers because you are a Muslim God. Had you been a Sikh God, you would have been more of a sport'" (Manto 16).

In the developments that take place a few days before the exchange Bishan Singh is visited by a Muslim friend from his village. Bishan Singh seems quite repulsed by the man initially but upon being told by one of the guards that the man was his old friend, Fazal Din who had come all the way to meet him he looks over Fazal Din and begins to mumble. Realising his friend's condition Fazal Din warmly placed his hand on Bishan Singh's shoulder telling him the news that his family was well and had managed to safely migrate to India. He had done whatever little he could to help.

Through all this, Bishan Singh keeps silent. So Fazal Din continues making efforts to converse with his friend. He tells Bishan Singh that he would also be moving to India in lieu of the new developments. He also requests Bishan Singh to tell the family that he

thought of them often and that they should write to him if there was anything he could do for them. But still troubled by his dilemma, Bishan Singh asks Fazal Din the question he had asked almost everyone: “Where is Toba Tek Singh?” (Manto 17). And finally as a reader one feels that he will get his much awaited reply but just the contrary happens. Though Fazal Din tells him that “...it is where it has always been,” probably implying that the land could not have moved or probably just out of his familiarity with the place (Manto 17).

But still curious Bishan Singh again asks, “In India or in Pakistan?” (Manto 17). It is the response of Fazal Din through which Manto manages to strike hard. It is the sense of utter confusion and alienation that the general public was subjected to in the face of the divided border lines that he wishes to communicate. As an initial response Fazal Din says, “[in] India,” but then within moments he reveals his doubt as he says “no, in Pakistan” (Manto 17). Bishan Singh’s angry distress can be gauged from his gibberish utterances.

And finally the day arrives, a winter evening that Manto categorically describes as cold, in the tradition of pathetic fallacy. As he narrates the saga of utter chaos and confusion, much like Salman Rushdie, he manages to instil a deep sense of “amputation” that partition entailed. He writes with a satirical tone of the behaviour of the inmates but the anguish and trauma of the people pierce through the reader’s imagination. He writes:

On a cold winter evening, buses full of Hindu and Sikh lunatics, accompanied by armed police and officials, began moving out of the Lahore asylum towards Wagah, the dividing line between India and Pakistan. Senior officials from the two sides in charge of exchange arrangements met, signed documents and the transfer got under way. It was quite a job getting the men out of the buses and handing them over to officials. Some just refused to leave. Those who were persuaded to do so began to run pell-mell in every direction. Some were stark naked. All efforts to get them to cover themselves had failed because they couldn’t be kept from tearing off their garments. Some were shouting abuse or singing. Others were weeping bitterly. Many fights broke out. (Manto 17)

It seems that such a behaviour is symptomatic of the trauma of the lunatics who metaphorically stand for the entire generation that had to stand witness to the historical event of partition.

While one feels traumatized by this poignant narration of “complete confusion,” Manto’s comment that the: “Female lunatics were also being exchanged and they were even noisier,” leaves a bad taste for feminist sensibility (Manto 17). It reflects the patriarchal mindset as “patriarchy itself traumatises women” (Horvitz 15). Manto’s position in this context is quite explicit as he places primarily male characters as lunatics, thereby challenging the tradition of placing of female characters as mentally afflicted and hysterical in illness narratives.

Manto further dramatizes the scene by emphasising the bitter cold in which the lunatic inmates appeared to be dead set against the will and operation of the two governments. It was difficult for them to fathom as to why they were being forcibly removed, being thrown into buses and driven to a strange place. Amidst this chaos slogans of “*Pakistan Zindabad*” and “*Pakistan Muradabad*” were also heard. There were fights taking place between certain inmates. But when Bishan Singh was brought out and he was asked to give his name for the record register all he could do was to repeat his question to the authorities: “Where is Toba Tek Singh? In India or Pakistan?” (Manto 18).

And finally, in that moment, amidst vulgar laughter, he learnt that it was in Pakistan. Hearing this, Bishan Singh tries to run but is overpowered by the Pakistani guards who are bent upon pushing him across the dividing line towards India. Manto interjects:

...he wouldn't move. 'This is Toba Tek Singh,' he announced. 'Uper the gur gur the annexe the be dhyana mung the dal of Toba Tek Singh and Pakistan.' (Manto 18)

While one clearly observes land being named after a human being here and the human becoming an unmoving-unresting piece of land, one also witnesses the urge within Bishan Singh, a prototype of a generation, literally infested with the insanity and loss felt by them in the face of partition, as he clings on to a piece of no-man's-land and declares it as Toba Tek Singh.

Manto creates a rather somber picture of the society governed by power structures as he depicts the lost efforts of many, who in vain, try to explain Bishan Singh that the land of Toba Tek Singh "had already been moved to India," or soon would be (Manto 18). The guards who tried to move him physically with force also have to eventually give up: "There he stood in no man's land on his swollen legs like a colossus" (Manto 18). His condition is the state of unassimilable experience—trauma. In other words, trauma experience is not experience, for experience and its assimilation requires a state of relaxation and a certain sense of claiming of that experience. Finally, realising how harmless the man was in his demands, he was allowed to stand in his proclaimed Toba Tek Singh while the exchange process continued and the night wore on.

In the final scene of the story, Bishan Singh screams loudly. The officials rush towards him and witness him collapse on the ground. The scene is reminiscent of the fainting of the witness in the Eichmann trial. Like the witness, Bishan Singh is not "deeply wounded" but is *re-traumatized*" (Shoshana Felman "A Ghost in the House of Justice: Death and the Language of Law" 257-258).

It may be looked upon as Bishan Singh's final "finding of voice" or "testimony" but only to collapse moments later, much like the Eichmann trial witness who was reliving the experience of the Nazi camp. Bishan Singh re-experienced the subdued pain of partition as the lunatics were being sent off to their respective lands. This can also be seen as a loss of the capacity to be a witness to oneself. The sense of loss of identity that triggered lunacy amongst the likes of Bishan Singh could be compared to that of Jews. The attempt to cling to no-man's-land can only be interpreted as a desperate attempt to hold on to one's identity without any state intervention—a clear defiance of state instilled insanity.

The narrative closes: "There, behind barbed wire, on one side, lay India and behind more barbed wire, on the other side, lay Pakistan. In between, on a bit of earth which had no name, lay Toba Tek Singh" (Manto 18). A scene that instils a profound sense of loss within the mind of the reader as well.

Perhaps then this last scene could be seen as a sight of "an encoded of the anti-past," being in "another temporality," and attempting to "restore something erased from the official text of history" (Mad Witnesses 83-84). While we as a generation are from the "*metatraumatic*" or "second-order traumatic," Manto shows the generation of Bishan Singh as "first-order traumatic."

The discussion surrounding Manto and Partition trauma cannot be considered complete as long as the debate about the question of universalisation of trauma and collectivised experience of remains. This is essentially an issue that arises from the understanding of trauma that "we are implicated in each other's trauma" (Caruth 24). Surely considering an entire generation as victim runs the risk of implicating everyone as a perpetrator. While it is difficult to be oblivious to the experiences of the first order traumatic or the second order traumatic, at the same time asking for reparations from the future generations of the perpetrators or holding every individual belonging to the then existent generation of the perpetrators as responsible are surely complex issues. But I leave that point of contestation as clue for future exploration and research.

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